

Installation manual for MLIP (Machine learning interatomic potential)

MLIP developed by Prof. Alexander Shapeev

Manual wrote by Yucheng Ji on November 15th 2022

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The directory structure:

➤ MLIP

1. Download the source file from Gitlab (Permission required).

下载 MLIP 源文件，该文件下载需要经过作者许可；

<https://gitlab.com/ashapeev/mlip-2>

2. Upload the source file to the destination path <MLIP> in your account.

上传源文件至目标路径 <MLIP>

```
tar -zxvf mlip-2-master
```

```
mv mlip-2-master mlip
```

3. Prepare the file and environments

预备文件目录及软件环境

```
module load 2022r2 intel/oneapi-all (DelftBlue)
```

```
module load 2022 intel-2022a (Snellius)
```

Attention:

If the version **2017 or 2018** Intel compiler is available, please use load this compiler!

4. Compile the source code

编译配置文件

```
cd mlip
```

```
./configure
```

```
Configure option:
```

```
--prefix=<path>          installation prefix path (e.g., /home/...)  
--prefix_fortran=<path>  install path to fortran  
--no-mpi                 disable MPI libraries [autodetect]  
--no-selftest           disable selftest implementation  
--lossless-cfg          turn on lossless configuration file writing  
--compiler=[intel|gnu]  which compilers to use [autodetect]  
--blas=NAME             BLAS library [autodetect]  
--program-suffix=<suffix> program name suffix
```

```
successfully created information
```

```
成功创建信息
```

```
Generating makefile configuration ...
```

```
Configuration complete.
```

5. compile the binary file

编译二进制文件

```
make mlp
```

there is no successfully created information, but the mlp compiled file can be found in the path as follows.

未有成功创建信息，但在以下路径可查询到 mlp 文件

```
./bin/mlp
```

6. Shortcomings of this solution

本方案的不足之处

a. Using mlp command, all testing cannot be passed!

使用 mlp 命令所有的测试均不通过!

```
make test
```

```
The output error is as follows,
```

```
输出错误如下
```

```
INTEGRATION TESTING:
```

```
Running test 00.convert_vasp_outcar
```

```
Abort(1090831) on node 0 (rank 0 in comm 0): Fatal error in PMPI_Init: Other MPI  
error, error stack:
```

```
MPIR_Init_thread(176):
MPID_Init(1430).....:
MPIR_pmi_init(167)...: PMI2_Job_GetId returned 14
make[1]: *** [Makefile:24:
/home/yuchengji/bin/mlp/mlip/test/examples/00.convert_vasp_outcar/test.sh] Error 1
make: *** [Makefile:173: test] Error 2
```

b. The normal mlp command should be used as follows,

常规 mlp 命令可使用如下:

```
mpirun -np 1 mlp convert-cfg --input-format=vasp-outcar OUTCAR out/relax.cfg
```

Instruction:

说明:

All commonly used mlp commands should be preceded by the beginning *mpirun -np 1*, these commands including *convert-cfg*, *calc-error*, *mindist*, *calc-efs*, *calc-grade*.

But the training mlp should be described according to the cores, such as *srun* or *mpirun -np 96*.

c. If the version of Intel compiler is 2017 or 2018, these shortcomings can be avoid.

使用 2017 或 2018 版本的 Intel 编译器可能会避免上述问题

7. Compile the libinterface for lammmps

为 lammmps 编译 mlp 接口

```
make libinterface
```

```
successfully created information
```

```
成功创建信息
```

```
ar: creating lib/lib_mlip_interface.a
```

8. Download the interface software from the Gitlab (Permission required)

下载 interface 接口程序, 需要作者允许

```
cd /home/yuchengji/bin/mlp/
```

```
git clone https://gitlab.com/ashapeev/interface-lammmps-mlip-2.git interface
```

9. Move the lib_mlip_interface.a file to the interface directory

移动生成的 mlp 库至 interface 文件夹

```
cd /home/yuchengji/bin/mlp/mlip/lib
```

```
mv lib_mlip_interface.a ../../interface/
```

➤ LAMMPS

1. Download the lammeps package

下载 lammeps 源文件

```
cd /home/yuchengji/bin/mlp/
```

```
git clone -b stable https://github.com/lammps/lammps.git lammps2022
```

2. Choose the package required

选择 LAMMPS 运行所需的包

```
cd /home/yuchengji/bin/mlp/lammps2022/src
```

```
make package-status
```

```
make yes-MC
```

```
make yes-MEAM
```

```
make yes-manybody
```

➤ Interface

1. Installing the mlip-lammps interface

安装 mlip 与 lammps 接口程序

```
cd /home/yuchengji/bin/mlp/interface
```

```
./install.sh ../lammps2022 intel_cpu_intelmpi
```

```
successfully created information
```

```
成功创建信息
```

```
text data bss dec hex filename  
10053427 235288 14312 10303027 9d3633 ../lmp_intel_cpu_intelmpi
```

```
make[1]: Leaving directory
```

```
'/home/yuchengji/bin/mlp/lammps2022/src/Obj_intel_cpu_intelmpi'
```

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Utilization manual for MLIP (Machine learning interatomic potential)

MLIP developed by Prof. Alexander Shapeev

Manual wrote by Yucheng Ji

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➤ Potential training

1. Transfer the VASP/OUTCAR to cfg file

转化 OUTCAR 为 MLIP cfg 文件

```
mlp convert-cfg --input-format=vasp-outcar OUTCAR Sc3Al.cfg
```

Note: All structure optimization step will be extracted into cfg file.

注释: 所有的在优化过程中的结构都会被考虑<一定变形>

The file format:

文件格式

BEGIN_CFG

Size

6

Supercell

7.604607 0.000002 -0.000001

0.000002 7.604608 -0.000007

-0.000001 -0.000007 7.604623

AtomData: id type cartes_x cartes_y cartes_z fx fy fz

1 0 2.851730 0.950570 2.851730 -0.000019 0.000003 0.000030

2 0 6.654030 6.654030 0.950570 0.000024 -0.000021 0.000001

3 0 4.752880 6.654030 2.851730 -0.000039 -0.000039 0.000021

4 0 0.950580 0.950580 0.950580 0.000030 -0.000015 -0.000009

5 0 2.851730 4.752880 6.654040 -0.000005 -0.000011 -0.000031

6 0 6.654030 2.851730 4.752890 0.000005 0.000021 -0.000009

Energy

-122.177426730000

PlusStress: xx yy zz yz xz xy

-0.33700 -0.33706 -0.33776 0.00029 0.00010 -0.00009

Feature EFS_by VASP

Feature mindist 2.688629

END_CFG

2. Summarize all cfg files to one train.cfg

综合所有的 cfg 文件成为一个文件

```
cat *.cfg >> train.cfg
```

3. Calculate the minimum distance in the train.cfg file

计算 train.cfg 文件中的原子最小间距

```
mlp mindist train.cfg
```

4. Copy and modify the initial.mtp file to the training directory

拷贝并编辑初始 mtp 文件

```
cp /home/yuchengji/bin/mlp/mlip/untrained_mtps/16.mtp .
```

```
vim 16.mtp
```

The file format:

文件格式

```
MTP
```

```
version = 1.1.0
```

```
potential_name = MTP1m
```

```
species_count = 1 # modify the number of elements
```

```
potential_tag =
```

```
radial_basis_type = RBChebyshev
```

```
min_dist = 2.38362 # modify the number to minimum distance
```

```
max_dist = 5 # modify the cut off distance
```

```
radial_basis_size = 8 # modify the number of radial basis functions, 8,6,10,4,12
```

```
radial_funcs_count = 2
```

```
radial_funcs_count = 4
```

```
alpha_moments_count = 350
```

```
alpha_index_basic_count = 130
```

```
Esc : wq
```

5. Compile the submit script file <Cluster required, e.g. DelftBlue>

编辑 submit 脚本<依据超算改变>

```
vim sub.sh
```

The content of submit script:

提交脚本内容

```
#!/bin/bash -l
```

```
#SBATCH --job-name="mlp"
```

```
#SBATCH --account=research-3me-mse
```

```
#SBATCH --partition=compute
```

```
#SBATCH -t 24:00:00
```

```
#SBATCH --nodes=1
#SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=24
#SBATCH --mem-per-cpu=2G

module load 2022r2
module load intel/oneapi-all

export OMP_NUM_THREADS=1 # Always be kept equal 1

srun mpirun -np 24 mlp train 16.mtp train.cfg --trained-pot-name=AlScCu.mtp
```

Esc : wq

6. Other train options provided in the mlp

Train 命令中其他选项

Options

```
--energy-weight=<double>: weight of energies in the fitting. Default=1
--force-weight=<double>: weight of forces in the fitting. Default=0.01
--stress-weight=<double>: weight of stresses in the fitting. Default=0.001
--scale-by-force=<double>: Default=0. If >0 then configurations near equilibrium (with
roughly force < <double>) get more weight.
--valid-cfgs=<string>: filename with configuration to validate
--max-iter=<int>: maximal number of iterations. Default=1000
--curr-pot-name=<string>: save potential on each iteration if <string> not empty
--trained-pot-name=<string>: filename for trained potential. Default=Trained.mtp_
--bfgs-conv-tol=<double>: stop if error dropped by a factor smaller than this over 50 BFGS
iterations. Default=1e-3
--weighting=<string>: how to weight configuration with different sizes relative to each other.
Default=vibrations. Other=molecules, structures
--init-params=<string>: how to initialize parameters if a potential was not pre-fitted. Default
is random. Other is same - this is when interaction of all species is the same (more accurate fit,
but longer optimization)
--skip-preinit: skip the 75 iterations done when parameters are not given
--update-mindist: updating the mindist parameter with actual minimal interatomic distance in
the training set
```

7. Submit the task to the cluster

提交任务至超算

```
sbatch sub.sh
```

output from mlp

mlp 程序输出

```

MTPR from 16.mtp, Database: train.cfg
Random initialization of radial coefficients
Rescaling...
  scaling = 0.8333333333333333, condition number = 2763.67306759096
  scaling = 0.909090909090909, condition number = 3673.61312437045
  scaling = 1, condition number = 5351.11880703349
  scaling = 1.1, condition number = 7834.47326839507
  scaling = 1.2, condition number = 10362.1760849044
Rescaling to 0.8333333333333333... done
Rescaling...
  scaling = 0.6944444444444445, condition number = 1637.70358193521
  scaling = 0.757575757575758, condition number = 2042.48285004521
  scaling = 0.8333333333333333, condition number = 2763.71502718135
  scaling = 0.916666666666667, condition number = 3778.30974868583
  scaling = 1, condition number = 5351.11880301559
Rescaling to 0.6944444444444445... done
Rescaling...
  scaling = 0.578703703703704, condition number = 942.573869338707
  scaling = 0.631313131313131, condition number = 1230.54333481382
  scaling = 0.6944444444444445, condition number = 1637.70358201451
  scaling = 0.763888888888889, condition number = 2093.96259982992

```

➤ MD Simulation without Active Learning

1. File required

所需文件

AlScCu.mtp	# potential	
mlip.ini	# potential	control file
train.cfg	# potential	original training file
data.Al	# lammmps	structure file
rdf.in	# lammmps	control file

2. The content of mlip.ini

mlip.ini 文件内容

```

mtp-filename all.mtp
calculate-efs FALSE
select FALSE
# select:threshold 2.1
# select:threshold-break 100.0
# select:save-selected preselect.cfg

```

```
# select:load-state state.als
```

3. Compile the submit script for MLIP-MD simulation

MLIP-MD 模拟的提交脚本

```
#!/bin/bash
#SBATCH --job-name="lmp_no_al"
#SBATCH --account=research-3me-mse
#SBATCH --partition=compute
#SBATCH -t 72:00:00
#SBATCH --nodes=4
#SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=12
#SBATCH --mem-per-cpu=5G

module load 2022r2
module load intel/oneapi-all

export OMP_NUM_THREADS=1

srun lmp_intel_cpu_intelmpi -in rdf.in
```

➤ MD Simulation with Active Learning

The flow of MLIP active learning.

MLIP 主动学习流程

1. File required

所需文件

all.mtp	# potential	
mlip.ini	# potential	control file
train.cfg	# potential	original training file
data.Al	# lammmps	structure file
rdf.in	# lammmps	control file
vasp_md_al.sh	# script	active learning script
al_vasp_calibration.py	# script	create vasp model
calculate_ab_initio_ef	# directory	vasp calculation
calculate_ab_initio_ef/raw_VASP_files	# directory	vasp INCAR KP...
data	# directory	lammmps data file

The directory structure of active learning

主动学习目录结构

1. Compile the vasp_md_al.sh file

编辑主动学习脚本

`vim vasp_md_al.sh`

The content of vasp_md_al.sh file

vasp_md_al.sh 文件内容

```
#!/bin/bash
```

```
#SBATCH --job-name="AL-ALScCu"
```

```
#SBATCH --account=research-3me-mse
```

```

#SBATCH --partition=compute
#SBATCH -t 72:00:00
#SBATCH --nodes=2
#SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=48
#SBATCH --mem-per-cpu=3G

module load 2022r2
module load intel/oneapi-all
export OMP_NUM_THREADS=1

mddir=/scratch/yuchengji/lammps/al_vasp_md
vaspdir=$mddir/calculate_ab_initio_ef
cd $mddir
touch $mddir/log.timestamp

rm -f train.cfg curr.mtp preselect.cfg diff.cfg selected.cfg out.cfg

cp all.mtp curr.mtp
cp train_init.cfg train.cfg

#A. Active set construction
mlp calc-grade curr.mtp train.cfg train.cfg out.cfg --als-filename=state.als
rm out.cfg

while [ 1 -gt 0 ]
do
#B. MD simulations and extrapolative (preselected) configurations
touch preselect.cfg
srun --job-name="int_job" --partition=compute --time=00:30:00 --ntasks=1 --cpus-per-task=8
--mem-per-cpu=1GB --pty lmp_intel_cpu_intelmpi -in rdf.in
#mpirun -np 2 lmp_intel_cpu_intelmpi -in rdf.in

n_preselected=$(grep "BEGIN" preselect.cfg | wc -l)
if [ $n_preselected -gt 0 ]; then
#C. Selection
mlp select-add curr.mtp train.cfg preselect.cfg diff.cfg --als-filename=state.als
cp diff.cfg $vaspdir
rm -f preselect.cfg
rm -f selected.cfg

#D and E. Ab initio calculations and merging (updating the training set)
cd $vaspdir

```

```

mlp convert-cfg diff.cfg outmodel --output-format=vasp-poscar
/home/yuchengji/bin/py39/bin/python3.9 al_vasp_calibration.py
for file in outmodel*
do
cd $vaspdir/mlp_al/$file
echo -e "VASP Calc : \c" >> $mddir/log.timestamp
date >> $mddir/log.timestamp
srun /home/yuchengji/bin/vasp/vasp_std_recompiled
energy=$( grep "TOTEN" OUTCAR | tail -n 1 | awk -F" " '{print $5}')
if [ $(echo "$energy < 10000" | bc) -eq 1 ];then
echo -e "VASP Calc : $mfile $energy \c" >> $mddir/log.timestamp
date >> $mddir/log.timestamp
mlp convert-cfg --input-format=vasp-outcar OUTCAR $mfile.cfg
cp $mfile.cfg $vaspdir
else
echo -e "VASP Calc : Error --> skipped \c" >> $mddir/log.timestamp
date >> $mddir/log.timestamp
fi
mlp convert-cfg --input-format=vasp-outcar OUTCAR $file.cfg

```

```

cd $vaspdir
done
cat *.cfg >> $mddir/train.cfg
rm -rf mlp_al diff.cfg outmodel* OUTCAR
cd $mddir

```

#F. Training

```

echo -e "MLIP Start : \c" >> $mddir/log.timestamp
date >> $mddir/log.timestamp
srun mlp train curr.mtp train.cfg --trained-pot-name=curr.mtp --update-mindist
echo -e "MLIP END : \c" >> $mddir/log.timestamp
date >> $mddir/log.timestamp

```

#A. Active set construction

```

mlp calc-grade curr.mtp train.cfg diff.cfg out.cfg --als-filename=state.als
rm -f diff.cfg
rm -f out.cfg

```

```

elif [ $n_preselected -eq 0 ]; then
exit
fi

```

done

2. Compile the al_vasp_calibration.py file and transfer the cfg file to the POSCAR
编辑 al_vasp_calibration.py 文件，将 cfg 格式转化为 POSCAR 格式

vim al_vasp_calibration.py

The content of al_vasp_calibration.py
al_vasp_calibration.py 文件内容

```
import os
import sys
import shutil
sys.path.append("/scratch/yuchengji/script/python/")
from lib import VASP_Structure as VS

model_list = []
ele_model = VS.CfgRead('diff.cfg')

for files in os.listdir('.'):
    if 'outmodel' in files:
        model_list.append(files)
if len(model_list) > 10:
    model_num = 10
else:
    model_num = len(model_list)

for i in range(model_num):
    model = model_list[i]
    model_path = './mlp_al/%s' %(model)
    if not os.path.exists(model_path):
        os.makedirs(model_path)
    poscar = VS.Cfg2Poscar(model, ['Al', 'Sc', 'Cu', 'H'], ele_model[i])

    with open('%s/POSCAR' %(model_path), 'w') as psc_w:
        psc_w.write("\n".join(poscar))
    try:
        shutil.copy('./raw_VASP_files/INCAR', '%s/INCAR' %(model_path))
        shutil.copy('./raw_VASP_files/KPOINTS', '%s/KPOINTS' %(model_path))
        shutil.copy('./raw_VASP_files/POTCAR', '%s/POTCAR' %(model_path))
        print("The %s model has been created" %(model))
    except Exception as err:
```

```
print(err)
```

```
print("The %s model creation failed!" %(model))
```

3. Submit the task to the cluster

向超算提交任务

```
sbatch vasp_md_al.sh
```

Good luck with your potential training!

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